

Here's a cyclone, there's a cyclone

Petrostates-interests' climate harm,
Gees I see now, Oh!
And from that harm they had some coin,
Gees I see now, Oh!
With a buck-buck here,
And a buck-buck there,
Here a cyclone, there a cyclone,
Everywhere a cat 3 cyclone

Petrostates-interests' climate harm,
Gees I see now, Oh!
And from that harm they accumulated power,
Gees I see now, Oh!
With a suppress-protest here,
And a stifle-resistance there,
Here an extortion, there a briber,
Everywhere a dissent-crusher

Petrostates-interests' climate harm,
Gees I see now, Oh!
And despite that harm they had some jobs-for-mates,
Gees I see now, Oh!
With a gobble-gobble here,
And a grovel-grovel there
Here a gobble, there a grovel,
Everywhere a gobble, grovel

Petrostates-interests' climate harm,
Gee I see now, Oh!
And to continue profiteering they distribute lies,
Gee I see now, Oh!
With an algorithm here,
And some clickbait there
Here an echo-chamber, there a hoax
Everyone a sheep-sheep,
Petrostates-interests' climate harm,
Gees I see now, Oh!

